
Locus of Control Orientation among B.Ed. Student-Teachers in Manipur: A Descriptive Study

***Sanasam Rakesh Singh** (Corresponding Author)

Research Scholar, Department of Teacher Education, Manipur University, Imphal, Manipur

Email: rak.sanasam@gmail.com

Dr. Chirom Shantikumar Singh

Assistant Professor, D.M. College of Teacher Education, Imphal, Manipur

Email: shantichirom@gmail.com

Wangkhem Lokeshwori Devi

M.Ed. M.A.(Education), M.A. History, Email: wangkhemlokeswori@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the locus of control orientation among student-teachers enrolled in the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) program in Manipur. Locus of control, a key psychological construct, refers to individuals' beliefs regarding the extent to which outcomes are contingent upon their own actions (internal locus of control) or external forces, such as luck, fate, or the actions of others (external locus of control) (Rotter, 1966). Given the complex and demanding nature of the teaching profession, understanding pre-service teachers' control beliefs is essential for fostering professional confidence, resilience, and effective classroom practices. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and employed a convenience sampling technique to collect data from 622 B.Ed. Student-teachers across selected teacher education institutions in Manipur. Data were gathered using the *Teacher Locus of Control Scale (TLOC)* developed by Rose and Medway (1981). Descriptive statistics, including frequency, percentage, median, standard deviation, and relative ratio, were used for data analysis. The

findings revealed a marginal predominance of internal locus of control, with 52% of the B.Ed. Student-teachers exhibited an internal orientation, and 48% showed an external orientation. The median score lay at the threshold of internal locus of control, indicating a balanced yet slightly internal control belief system among the trainees. The study highlights the need for teacher education programs to consciously nurture an internal locus of control through reflective practices and mastery experiences, thereby enhancing pre-service teachers' professional efficacy and adaptability.

Introduction:

The *locus of control* (LOC) concept refers to the degree to which individuals believe that they have control over the outcomes of events in their lives. People with an internal locus of control attribute outcomes to their own abilities, effort, or actions, while those with an external locus of control tend to attribute outcomes to external factors such as luck, fate, or the actions of others (Rotter, 1966). The concept has been widely studied in various fields, including psychology, education, and organizational behavior, as it can influence motivation, decision-making, and overall well-being (Lefcourt, 1982). For prospective teachers—individuals in the process of preparing for a career in teaching—the locus of control plays an important role in shaping their attitudes toward teaching, their professional identity, and their ability to handle the challenges of the profession. Teaching is a complex, dynamic profession that requires not only subject matter expertise but also adaptability, resilience, and effective classroom management. Teachers' beliefs about their ability to influence students' learning outcomes can significantly affect their teaching practices and interactions with students (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 1998).

Research indicates that teachers with an internal locus of control are more likely to engage in proactive behaviors, take responsibility for student outcomes, and exhibit greater job satisfaction (Brock & Grady, 1998). In contrast, teachers with an external locus of control may struggle with feelings of helplessness, stress, and burnout, particularly when faced with challenges that seem beyond their control (Zimmerman, 1990). Therefore, understanding the locus of control in prospective teachers is crucial for informing teacher preparation programs and interventions designed to foster resilience and professional competence.

The relationship between locus of control (LOC) and B.Ed Student-teachers has been explored in various studies; however, the impact of LOC in the context of teacher training remains an area of growing interest. Research has suggested that prospective teachers' locus of control can be influenced by their prior educational experiences, their expectations of the teaching profession, and the pedagogical approaches they encounter in their training programs (Calik & Kocer, 2011). Given the demanding nature of teacher preparation and the various challenges prospective teachers face, it is essential to explore how LOC affects their development and how teacher education programs can nurture internal LOC to promote confidence and resilience in the classroom.

Literature Review

Studies have consistently shown that **pre-service teachers with an internal locus of control exhibit higher motivation and responsibility toward student learning**. Research on locus of control has consistently highlighted its influence on teachers' professional beliefs and classroom practices. Teachers with an internal locus of control tend to attribute student success to their own instructional efforts, persistence, and pedagogical decisions rather than to external forces such as luck or student background (Rose & Medway, 1981). Such beliefs are associated with proactive teaching behaviours, greater responsibility for student outcomes, and higher levels of job satisfaction (Brock & Grady, 1998). Studies have also shown that individuals with an internal orientation demonstrate stronger persistence and problem-solving abilities, which, in teacher education contexts, translate into effective classroom management and adaptive instructional strategies (Findley & Cooper, 1983). In contrast, an external locus of control has been linked to increased stress, feelings of helplessness, and professional burnout, particularly when teachers perceive classroom challenges as beyond their influence (Zimmerman, 1990). Among pre-service teachers, locus of control plays a very important role in shaping confidence, instructional decision-making, and inclusive teaching attitudes. Internally oriented pre-service teachers report higher confidence in managing diverse learners and students with learning difficulties (Soodak & Podell, 1996) and tend to adopt flexible, student-centred teaching approaches (Cheng, 1994). Research has also demonstrated a strong relationship between locus of control and teacher self-efficacy, suggesting that teachers who perceive greater personal control are more resilient and capable of coping with professional demands (Severino et al., 2011; Woolfolk Hoy, 2007). Evidence from India supports these findings, indicating that pre-service teachers with an internal locus of control show significantly higher teaching competence and academic engagement than their externally oriented peers (Kulshrestha & Pandey, 2013). Moreover, variations in locus of control and teacher efficacy across demographic

variables, such as age and experience, suggest that over time these beliefs evolve and may be shaped through teacher education programs (Merwe, 2013). Hence, the present study aims to investigate the Locus of Control orientation among B.Ed. Student-teachers in Manipur.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the **internal and external locus of control orientations** among B.Ed. Student-teacher in Manipur.
2. To analyse the **distribution and central tendency** of locus of control scores among B.Ed. Student-teachers.
3. To identify the **dominant locus of control orientation** among B. Ed student-teachers in the study sample.

Hypotheses

- **H₀₁**: There is no significant predominance of internal locus of control over the external locus of control among B. Ed Student-teachers in Manipur.
- **H₀₂**: The locus of control scores of B. Ed Student-teachers does not show meaningful central tendency or consistency.

Methodology

Research Design and Sample

The present study adopted a **cross-sectional research design** to examine the locus of control orientation among pre-service teachers. A **convenience sampling technique** was employed due to accessibility and feasibility considerations. The sample comprised **622 B.Ed. Student-teachers** enrolled in teacher education institutions located in **Manipur**. Efforts were made to ensure that the sample adequately represented student-teachers pursuing the Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) programme in the selected institutions.

Instrument Used

Data were collected using the **Teacher Locus of Control (TLOC) Scale** developed by **Rose and Medway (1981)**. The scale consists of **28 forced-choice items**, each presenting two alternative explanations for classroom situations involving student success or failure. Of the total 28 items, fourteen describe situations of student success, and fourteen describe situations of student failure. For each success situation, one option attributes the outcome internally to the teacher's effort or instructional behavior. In contrast, the alternative attributes it to external factors, typically related to student characteristics or situational variables. Similarly, for failure situations, one option reflects an internal teacher attribution and the other assigns responsibility to external causes. Scores are obtained by summing the number of internal attributions, with higher scores indicating a stronger internal locus of control. **Rose and Medway (1981)** reported satisfactory internal consistency for the scale, with a Kuder–Richardson (KR-20) reliability coefficient of 0.83, indicating good reliability for research purposes. The instrument has been widely used in educational research and is considered appropriate for assessing locus of control in teacher education contexts.

Procedures

The present study aimed to examine the locus of control among pre-service teachers in Manipur using the **Teachers' Locus of Control Scale developed by Rose and Medway (1981)**. Data collection was carried out systematically through the following steps.

First, a **preliminary survey** was conducted to identify teacher education colleges located in the valley districts of Manipur. Information regarding student enrolment was collected to estimate the potential number of respondents and to plan the logistics of data collection.

Second, **formal permission** was obtained from the principals of the selected teacher education institutions. The purpose of the study, along with its purely academic nature, was clearly explained to the institutional authorities to ensure transparency and compliance with ethical standards.

Third, a **convenient date and time** for administering the scale were scheduled in consultation with the principals and concerned teacher educators. Care was taken to ensure that the data collection process did not interfere with regular instructional activities.

Fourth, the **28-item Teacher Locus of Control Scale (TLOC)** was administered to the B.Ed. Student-teachers in their respective classroom settings. Prior to administration, participant were informed about the study and assured that their responses would remain **confidential**. Clear instructions were provided regarding the method of responding to the items using the given response options. Student-teachers were informed that there are **no right or wrong answers** and were encouraged to respond honestly based on their personal beliefs and attitudes.

The administration of the scale required approximately **20–25 minutes** to complete. The researchers remained present throughout the process to clarify doubts, ensure independent responding, and confirm the completeness of the responses.

The study uses a **cross-sectional research design**, with data collected at a single point in time, and a **convenience sampling technique** was used.

Statistical Techniques

The data collected were analysed using **SPSS Statistics (Version 28)**. Descriptive statistical techniques were employed in accordance with the study's objectives. The following statistical measures were used:

- **Frequency and percentage analysis** to determine the prevalence of internal and external locus of control orientations.
- **Median and standard deviation** to describe the central tendency and dispersion of locus of control scores.
- **Relative ratio** to compare the proportion of student-teachers with internal and external locus of control orientations

Result

Table 1: Prevalence of the Internal and External Locus of Control of the study sample

Locus of Control	Frequency	Percentage	Relative ratio (Internal: External)
Internal	326	52	

External	296	48	1.10: 1
Total	622	100	

The internal and external locus of control

Figure 1: Internal and External Orientation

Table 1: The table shows the frequencies and percentages of internal and external locus of control among B.Ed. Students. Trainees in Manipur. Of the 622 respondents, 326 individuals (52%) exhibited a strong tendency toward internal locus of control, while the remaining 296 respondents (48%) were inclined toward external locus of control. The relative ratio of internal to external locus of control was found to be 1.10:1, demonstrating that for every 100 trainees with an external locus of control, there were roughly 110 trainees with an internal locus of control. This indicates a marginal prevalence of internal locus of control over external one within the sample.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Locus of Control of the study samples

Locus of control	N	Minimum	Maximum	Median	Std. D
	622	7	23	16.00	2.77

As shown in Table 2, the **median locus of control score** of the sample was **16.00**, with a **standard deviation of 2.77**. The minimum and maximum scores ranged from **7 to 23**, indicating moderate

variability among respondents. The median score lying at the threshold of internal locus of control reflects a **balanced but slightly internally oriented belief system** among B.Ed. Student-teachers.

Discussion

The present study examined the locus of control orientation among B.Ed. Student-teachers in Manipur revealed a marginal predominance of an internal locus of control over an external locus of control. Specifically, 52% of respondents demonstrated an internal orientation, while 48% exhibited an external orientation, with a relative ratio of 1.10:1. This finding suggests that although internal locus of control slightly outweighs external orientation, the difference is not substantial, indicating a near-balanced control belief system among pre-service teachers.

The observed predominance of internal locus of control is consistent with Rotter's (1966) theoretical proposition that individuals who perceive outcomes as contingent upon their own actions tend to develop stronger motivational and achievement-oriented behaviors. In the context of teacher education, this internal orientation is particularly significant, as it reflects student-teachers' belief in their ability to influence classroom processes and student learning outcomes through personal effort and instructional competence. Similar findings have been reported in earlier studies, which indicate that teachers with an internal locus of control are more proactive, reflective, and resilient in their professional roles (Brock & Grady, 1998; Severino et al., 2011; Hans et al., 2017).

The median locus of control score of 16.00, lying at the threshold of internal control, further reinforces the notion that B.Ed. Student-teachers in Manipur possess a moderately internalized belief system. However, the moderate standard deviation ($SD = 2.77$) and the nearly equal distribution of internal and external orientations suggest considerable variability within the sample. This variability may be attributed to differences in prior schooling experiences, socio-cultural contexts, exposure to teaching practice, and individual perceptions of the teaching profession. Earlier research has indicated that pre-service teachers' control beliefs are shaped not only by personal traits but also by the nature of their training environments and opportunities for mastery experiences (Calik & Kocer, 2011).

The substantial proportion of student-teachers exhibiting an external locus of control (48%) is a noteworthy finding and warrants careful consideration. An external orientation among future teachers may reflect uncertainty, limited classroom exposure, or perceived constraints within the educational system. Teachers with stronger external control beliefs may be more likely to attribute student success or

failure to factors such as students' background, institutional limitations, or chance, which can potentially hinder instructional initiative and professional confidence (Zimmerman, 1990). This underscores the importance of teacher education programmes in consciously addressing psychological constructs alongside pedagogical skills.

The study findings also align with research highlighting the close association between locus of control and teacher self-efficacy. Studies have consistently demonstrated that internal locus of control is positively related to higher self-efficacy, stress management, and adaptive coping strategies among teachers (Ashagi & Beheshtifar, 2015; Cascio et al., 2014). Although self-efficacy was not directly examined in the present study, the slightly internal orientation observed among the participants suggests a foundational belief in personal agency that can be further strengthened through structured interventions during teacher preparation.

The results indicate that while B.Ed. Student-teachers in Manipur show a tendency toward an internal locus of control; this orientation is still developing and not firmly consolidated. This transitional pattern is expected in B.Ed. Students-teachers who are in the early stages of professional identity formation. Therefore, teacher education institutions play a critical role in fostering stronger internal control beliefs by providing reflective teaching experiences, constructive feedback, mentoring, and opportunities for successful classroom engagement.

Conclusion

The present study confirms that an **internal locus of control** is marginally more prevalent than an external orientation among B.Ed. Student-teachers in Manipur. Specifically, **52%** of the participants demonstrated an internal orientation, while 48% showed an external orientation. With a median score of **16.00**—located at the threshold of internal control—the findings reveal a balanced yet slightly internally oriented belief system among the trainees. This suggests that these prospective teachers generally maintain a moderate belief in their capacity to influence student outcomes through personal effort and professional competence. The significance of these findings lies in the established link between a teacher's control beliefs and their professional effectiveness. Research consistently indicates that teachers with internal locus of control are more likely to take responsibility for student outcomes, engage in proactive instructional behaviors, and experience greater job satisfaction. Conversely, the substantial minority (48%) exhibiting an external orientation may be more susceptible to stress, burnout, and feelings of helplessness when faced with classroom challenges they perceive as beyond their control. The

study concludes that **internal locus of control is marginally more prevalent than external locus of control among B.Ed. Student-teachers in Manipur**. The findings suggest that B.Ed. Student-teachers generally possess a moderate belief in their ability to influence outcomes through personal effort and competence. The study highlights the importance of psychological constructs in shaping the professional development of future teachers.

Limitations

1. The present study was limited to **B.Ed. student-teachers from Manipur**, which restricts the generalizability of the findings to other regions.
2. Only **descriptive statistics** were employed; inferential analysis could provide deeper insights.
3. The present study focused solely on locus of control and did not empirically examine its relationship with self-efficacy or other psychological variables.

Future Research Directions

Based on the findings of the present study, the following recommendations are suggested for future research and practice. Future studies may examine locus of control in relation to other important psychological constructs, such as teacher self-efficacy, motivation, job satisfaction, emotional intelligence, resilience, and burnout, to obtain a more comprehensive understanding of teacher effectiveness. Longitudinal studies are recommended to examine how locus of control orientations **develop and change over time** during teacher training and early teaching careers, particularly in response to professional experiences. Replicating the study with a larger and more diverse sample across different states or regions of India would enhance the generalizability of the findings and allow for meaningful regional or cultural comparisons. Future research may also compare **pre-service and in-service teachers**, or teachers from different disciplines and educational levels, to identify variations in locus of control orientations across professional stages. Experimental or quasi-experimental studies may be conducted to assess the effectiveness of **teacher education interventions**—such as reflective practice, mentoring, and mastery experience training—in fostering an internal locus of control among pre-service teachers. Future research should explore how teacher education curricula can be structured to

systematically promote internal locus of control, thereby strengthening self-efficacy, professional confidence, and classroom effectiveness.

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Conflicting Interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicting interests regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Data Availability

Yes, upon reasonable request.

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